

Will Shenzhen become a hotspot for marine invasive species?

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Abstract

Invasive species are becoming a major problem as globalization has increased in recent years, particularly affecting port cities like Shenzhen in China. Not much research has been conducted to monitor marine invasive species in the area around Shenzhen, and there are still many uncertainties. This article examines the general process of invasion and characteristics of highly invaded areas, analyzes the various natural and human-related factors that could make Shenzhen a hotspot for marine invasive species in the future, and discusses the potential consequences of marine invasive species in Shenzhen and actions to be taken to prevent these consequences.

1. Introduction

In recent years, the threat of invasive species has grown with the increase in globalization, with port cities like Shenzhen, China, being the most affected. However, little research to monitor marine invasive species has been conducted in the area surrounding Shenzhen, so not much is known regarding this topic. This article aims at discussing whether or not Shenzhen will become a hotspot for invasive species, and the consequences and potential policies in the face of the threat of invasive species.

2. The Process of Invasion

Before whether Shenzhen will become a hotspot for invasive species can be discussed, a definition of the term "invasive species", as well as examination of the invasion process, is needed. An invasive species is an introduced species to an environment that becomes overpopulated and causes ecological damage to this new environment. To become an invasive species, a species has to go through several stages [1]. First, the species has to reach a suitable location, usually on human trade vessels, while surviving the journey. The species is then referred to as an introduced species. If the species is being contained for use by humans, it needs to escape this captivity into the wider ecosystem. The species then needs to adapt to this new environment in order for it to

be able to survive under new environmental and ecological conditions. Once a species starts reproducing without human intervention, it is referred to as an established species. In this ecosystem, the species will need to spread across a larger range and cause economic or ecological issues for it to then be considered an invasive species [1].

3. Characteristics of Potentially Invasive Species

When considering whether an area is at risk of invasive species, several characteristics that make non-native species potentially invasive should be considered. Invasive species usually reproduce very quickly and very early on in their life cycle [1], enabling them to multiply quickly and out-compete any native species that occupy the same ecological niche. In addition, invasive animal species usually have a generalist diet and are found in a wide range of environments in their native range, which allows them to more easily survive in new environments they have not been exposed to. Although high intelligence isn't a shared trait of all invasive animals, it usually correlates to more complex and flexible behavior, making it easier for species to behaviorally adapt to different environments. A human-related characteristic that most invasive species share is that they are introduced to the new environment in large numbers and even multiple times [1], leading to a higher rate of success for the species to establish in the new environment.

4. Characteristics of Highly Invaded Regions

Another perspective can be obtained by analyzing the characteristics shared by regions with large numbers of invasive species. Typically, less biodiverse environments are easier to invade than more biodiverse ones, as there are fewer organisms that could pose a threat to any potential invasive species, as well as more vacant niches that the invader can occupy. The extent of human impact on an environment is a major factor in the number of invasive species, so locations important for trade, tourism, and resource extraction (including fishing and mariculture) are relatively easy to invade. This is because the extent of human disturbance in an area correlates directly with the chance of a

species being introduced by humans. Moreover, the populations of native organisms in locations with human disturbance are usually damaged by human activity, leaving vacant niches, which allow non-native species to fill these niches and more easily establish themselves in the ecosystem. As a result of these factors, the environments with the lowest numbers of invasive species are usually the most isolated ones.

These factors can easily be spotted when looking at invasive species in the 3 main marine regions in Europe and the number of invasive species in these regions [1]. The Mediterranean Sea with its 569 established non-native species is a hub of international trade, and many non-native marine species are farmed there as well. It has also recently been connected to the Red Sea via the Suez Canal, creating a path for even more non-native species to be introduced [2]. The Atlantic coast of Europe has around 200 established non-native species, mainly centered around the British Isles and the Northern coast of France, which are significant trading areas. The Baltic Sea is significantly less invaded but still has 62 established non-native species. In addition to these human factors, there are also some natural factors that influence how easily a region is to invade. The diversity of substrates to attach to and the availability of vacant niches can both improve the chances for a species to establish in a region.

5. Is Shenzhen a Hotspot for Invasive Species?

Shenzhen is a very vulnerable location to invasive species and there are several reasons for this. Coastal seas in general are one of the most vulnerable ecosystems to invasions, because they are usually the areas with the most human disturbance. Shenzhen is very connected to other regions of the world as it has the 4th biggest port in the world, seeing traffic of 30 million twenty-foot equivalent units (TEUs) annually [3]. Since international trade is one of the most important ways that invasive species spread, large ports like Shenzhen generally introduce a large number of invasive species to the surrounding area. Ecosystems near ports are also very vulnerable to human disturbance, so there may be more niches vacated by native species whose populations have decreased.

Another hub of trade quite comparable to Shenzhen, although perhaps not as busy as Shenzhen, is London, its port ranking 64th globally with 3.2 million TEUs annually [3]. The LISI (London Invasive Species Initiative) has monitored invasive species extensively, kept track of the invasive species in and around London [4], providing additional information on invasive species around similar large ports. The LISI has a list of invasive species in London, which contains over 70 species, showing that port cities like London and Shenzhen are very susceptible to invasive species. However, there is a key difference between the environ-

ments of London and Shenzhen, which is that as London is not a coastal city, all aquatic invasive species in London are freshwater species that are established in the river Thames and not the sea. This means that they cannot be transported from other countries by attaching themselves to ship hulls, as they would have to pass through the ocean, the conditions of which they cannot tolerate. This makes London potentially harder to invade than Shenzhen, implying that Shenzhen may have even more invasive species.

In recent years, tourism has also been growing in Shenzhen, and Shenzhen ranked second among cities to visit by Lonely Planet in 2019 [5]. An increase in tourism will increase human disturbance in local ecosystems, and tourists may also introduce non-native species to Shenzhen from where they came from. One of the tourist attractions in Shenzhen, although not extremely popular, is going to the beach, which causes even more human disturbance in the coastal regions, and thus makes these areas more vulnerable to invasive species [5].

In addition, there are some natural factors that make the marine ecosystems around Shenzhen very easy for many non-native species to survive and therefore establish in. Firstly, Shenzhen has a water salinity of about the global average for seawater, so it is not a particularly challenging environment for non-native marine species to invade. The area has mangrove forests, which are not a particularly harsh environment. Also, the waters around Shenzhen in particular are very rich in nutrients due to nutrient-rich discharge from the nearby Pearl River, making it easier for any introduced species to survive.

6. The Consequences

Aside from consequences in Shenzhen, an invasive species in Shenzhen can also cause unwanted consequences elsewhere in the South China Sea, as they can spread to other areas using the methods which they used to travel to Shenzhen in the first place. However, invasive species can also travel down the coast of the South China Sea using the Coriolis Effect, which is a result of the Earth's rotation. In the part of the Northern hemisphere where Shenzhen is located, both winds and ocean currents move westwards. This means that any invasive species which manages to establish on the Shenzhen coast will be able to travel to, for example, Vietnam, which is further west along the coast.

This is because most benthic organisms have a planktonic stage in their life cycle. In the case of crustaceans, including barnacles, their nauplius larvae are free-floating in the water column, feeding on algae. The trochophore larvae of sessile molluscs are also planktonic, and so are the planulae of cnidarian species like corals. This planktonic stage allows most sessile organisms to move along ocean currents, and if they are invasive, they can use this to establish far beyond their introduced location.

7. Actions Which Should be Taken

In terms of controlling invasive species, the government should follow and enforce the UN Ballast Water Convention, a set of regulations introduced by the International Maritime Organisation (IMO) in 2004 to minimise and eventually eliminate the problem of invasive species transported through ballast water. The IMO is a United Nations department which regulates cargo shipping, and the Ballast Water Convention includes standards for ballast water of ships and requires each ship to keep a record of measurements taken of their ballast water, and also requires ships to change their ballast water at least 200 nautical miles from land and in water deeper than 200 meters, in order that the larval organisms in that ballast water not be introduced to coastal waters where they can become established [6]. It also encourages ships to install ballast water treatment systems.

Shenzhen could also use underwater robots to inspect ships for biofouling before allowing them to enter the ports. There is a robot called the Sentinus Inwater Inspection Robot, which automatically captures video footage while it scans the hull of a ship, using AI to determine which areas it has already recorded footage from, eventually covering the whole ship [7]. Also, as is already the case in London, research should be conducted to monitor the status of various invasive and potentially invasive species in the area.

8. Summary and Future Prospects

Shenzhen is at a high risk to invasive species and will be in trouble in the future if actions are not taken. One potentially invasive species that has been recently discovered on the coast of Shenzhen is the barnacle *Megabalanus coccopoma*, and in the future, we will investigate if it has been established already and how this can affect the ecosystem.

References

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